

Complementary approaches in characterization of secondary raw materials: A case study of H₂-reduced bauxite residue

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Abstract

Applying commonly used characterization techniques for secondary-type materials is generally challenging because of pre-processed treatments and particle surface contaminations. For this reason, the current work aims at presenting combination of micro-computed tomography (μ CT), thermomagnetic analysis (TMA) and X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) as a supplementary approach for the SEM-based automated mineralogy (AM). To this end, an H₂-reduced bauxite residue was characterized in this research work to identify its complex compositions. Further, the sample was subjected to different magnetic (Slon[®], Davis Tube) and gravity (Mozley Table) separators feasibly examine iron recoverability from the H₂-reduced sample. The qualitative results obtained from μ CT showed that the reduced bauxite residue (red mud) was composed of only magnetite disseminated in fine grain sizes. It was well correlated with the AM outcomes. Further, coupled information of TMA, XRD and μ -CT provided complementary results for the secondary type materials, which was very useful for downstream processes (i.e., magnetic and gravity separations). The experimental results obtained for the applied separators disclosed that the Mozley Table could potentially increase the Fe content from 21-23% to 31%, with the mass recovery of 52%. Test results using the Slon[®] at 1000 G displayed almost similar Fe content (33%) with the maximum mass recovery of 80%. Applying the single stage Davis Tube at a lower magnetic intensity of 2500 G showed around 18% improvement in the Fe grade (from 22 to 40%), while the mass recovery was the lowest (22%) among all the equipment tested. It was finally highlighted that multi-stage medium magnetic separation followed with one-two scavenging and cleaning stages can potentially elevate the grade and recovery of iron.

Keywords: H₂-reduced bauxite residue, red mud, thermomagnetic analysis (TMA), micro-computed tomography (μ CT), automated mineralogy.

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, extraction of valuable elements from secondary resources has been always attractive for many industries. Through this, not only a massive amount of waste material can be

valorized but specifically also a significant amount of critical and invaluable elements can be potentially re-used in the concept of the circular economy. In this regard, aluminium (Al) industry is not an exception and ca. 175 million m³ of bauxite residue (BR), so-called red mud, is stocked in the tailing dams annually (Archambo and Kawatra, 2022), which creates severe environmental issues globally (e.g., water/air pollutions, and tailing dam collapses). The major components of such disposals are iron oxides, mainly hematite (Fe₂O₃), which includes 35-60 wt% of BR in overall. The global stockpile of red mud is estimated nearly 4 billion tons (Archambo and Kawatra, 2022) indicating on ca. 800 million tons of iron presuming 40 wt% Fe on average. Although over the last three decades, researchers used various techniques to recover iron from bauxite residues (Rai et al., 2019; Cardenia et al., 2021), to the best of the author's knowledge, there is so far no approach available to economically extract it with acceptable grade and mass recovery.

The current tendency to produce iron is toward decarbonization of the entire process using mainly hydrogen to lower CO₂ emissions (Patisson et al., 2021). However, there is a serious lack of knowledge regarding sample characterization under different reduction conditions and downstream processes. Without a deep understanding of sample properties, it is certainly challenging to apply appropriate separation techniques. Accurate perception from such heterogeneous fine particulate systems strongly requires a precise and appropriate mineralogy characterization approach. Recent developments indicated that X-ray computed micro-tomography (μ CT) and SEM-based automated mineralogy (AM) have been extensively utilized to characterize a variety of particle properties in the scope of process mineralogy for coarse and fine particle sizes, respectively (Evans et al., 2015). The μ CT is a non-invasive 3D technique that allows to image the distribution of minerals inside a sample, while scanning electron microscopy-based methods (e.g., MLA and QEMSCAN - quantitative evaluation of materials by scanning electron microscopy (SEM)) allows for a 2D quantitative analysis of mineral essays by combining backscattering electron (BSE) images with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (Reyes et al., 2017). The low resolution (tens of micrometers) and the lack of chemical information have typically limited the application of μ CT to identify and analyze fine particles. Nevertheless, it remains unclear how coarse a particle must be to be accurately measured by the μ CT (Hassanzadeh et al., 2019). Thus, its applicability in mineral processing, particularly for determining particle size distribution, liberation degree, texture, pore sizes, and micro-cracks, has been relatively limited with respect to similar attenuations between mineral phases, inadequate resolution, and lack of an automated mineralogical analysis software. For example, Guntoro et al., (2019) showed that the main limitation of this approach lies in the dataset itself, in which there was a significant overlap in grayscale values between chalcopyrite and pyrite in studied samples. For fine particles, it unavoidably suffers from a stereological bias along with a statistical dispersion in the light of number of analyzed particles (Ueda et al., 2016), which results in an overestimation of mineral liberation degrees. Moreover, there are natural uncertainties inherently linked to representativity and sample preparation shortcomings (Evans and Napier-Munn, 2013). Nowadays, most of the studies in mineral processing rely on mainly one

mineralogical approach (e.g., AM) (Leißner et al., 2016; Hoang et al., 2019; Fernandes et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2022) which does not seem to be a solid approach for obtaining precious information from heterogeneous samples. For this reason, the present work uses three supplementary approaches to explore relatively accurate qualitative and quantitative information from a secondary resource (H₂-reduced bauxite residue).

Since there is very little information about using H₂-reduced bauxite residue from processing perspective, this work, for the first time, employs a combination of micro-computed tomography (μ CT), SEM-automated mineralogy (AM), and thermomagnetic analyses (TMA). Separation treatment methods, including low, medium, and high-intensity magnetic separations, as well as gravity processes, were applied to recover iron from the H₂-reduced bauxite residue.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

H₂-reduced (500 °C and 5 vol% hydrogen at 500 °C and 2 h with 20 wt% NaOH) samples were received in the form of pellets with the size of 1-2 cm and were directly subjected to size reduction and classifications. Detailed information regarding the reduction procedure by hydrogen, and thermal treatment conditions can be found elsewhere (Pilla et al., 2022). Samples were ground using a laboratory jaw crusher (Retsch®, Germany). Prior to crushing and as a normal procedure, the jaw crusher was cleaned up a couple of times with quartz and then ethanol to prevent any external contamination. The ground samples were classified by a dry sieving method (RX-29H&B, ROT-AP®, W.S. Tyler, U.S.A.) applying 50 g per run which lasted 15 min. The following screens (16# (1168 μ m), 30# (500 μ m), 60# (210 μ m), 150# (105 μ m)) (Tyler standards, Retsch®, Germany) were selected for sieve analyses. To ensure the performance of sieving, the particle size distribution of fraction size (<105 μ m) was measured by the laser particle size analyzer (LPSA, Mastersizer 3000, United Kingdom). After comminution and classification stages and reaching desirable size fractions, the samples were subjected to magnetic and gravity separation. Since all separation methods were applied in a wet environment, the products of each test (i.e., non-magnetic and magnetic ones) were first filtered using a filter press (MACSLAB, Eriez, F-Press model), dried (overnight at 60 °C), and ultimately analyzed by the XRF technique.

2.2. Micro-computed tomography (μ CT) measurements

All μ CT scans were performed using a Nikon XT-H 225™ and Nikon InspectX software. This scanner was equipped with a fixed 25-225 kV/0-1000 μ A X-ray source. It generates a polychromatic cone beam and has a minimum focal spot size of 3 μ m. The detector produced 2850×2850 pixel radiographs with up to 65000 greyscale values. The scanning parameters in this study were chosen in a way to optimize the spatial resolution and enable to recognize the shape of individual grains. Scanning for all samples was performed at voltage of 100 kV, current=70 μ A, exposure of 1420 ms, and grain=18 dB. The scans were produced by combining 8955 projections, while the samples were continuously rotated 360°. The following image analysis was post-processed using Dragonfly from Object Research Systems. The

voxel resolution of the scans is dependent on distances between the X-ray source, sample, and detector. The sample size of the trans-vertical epoxy pucks, prepared for SEM, used in this study allowed for a voxel resolution of 5 μm .

2.3. X-ray diffraction (SQ-XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

For semi-quantitative X-ray diffraction analyses (SQ-XRD), a representative 10 g of target samples including feed, non-magnetic and magnetic specimens were ground in an agate-type laboratory disc mill (Siebtechnik, Germany) for 1 min after cleaning the discs carefully with glass beads and ethanol. The prepared samples were later washed up with 10 mL of ethanol, pulverized for 2 min, and finally dried overnight in an oven (60 °C). A Bruker D8-Advance Series 2 XRD equipment was utilized for the measurements, and Diffrac.eva V.6.0 and Topas software were applied for mineral phase identifications and quantification. The samples were scanned in the θ range of 5- 80° under the Co K α radiation.

Primary X-ray fluorescence measurements were carried out using a handheld Portable XRF analyzer (pXRF, Thermal Science, XL3t). A representative 3 g of sample was prepared under a specific condition and three measurements were performed from three different locations on the surface of sample. The average content was reported as the final value.

Metallic ions existing in the feed sample were analyzed using ICP-HR-MS Element 2 (Thermo) equipped with an auto-sampler SC2 DX dust-covered with a ULPA filter. For this measurement, 0.5 g of the powder was used and dissolved in nitric acid (HNO₃). The error was no more than 10% as estimated by duplicating random points and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

2.4. SEM -automated mineralogy (AM)

A representative 2 g of the feed sample was put into a small glass container. Later, ca. 0.5 g graphite was added, and the entire sample was homogenized by manual shaking for 5-10 min. It was later mounted in epoxy and subsequently polished to create a regular 25 mm polished section, which was then cut into four, and put into the 30 mm mound. Afterwards, using epoxy again, 30 mm polished sections were created. For the SEM analyses, a 10 nm carbon coating was applied to the sample surface. Prior to the automated analyses, the sample was manually investigated using the ZEISS Sigma 300VP field emission SEM at GEUS that was equipped with 2 Bruker Xflash, 129 eV energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS) detectors and a Bruker e-Flash FS EBSD detector. The SEM included the automated mineralogy software platform Mineralogic from ZEISS for AQM-SEM analyses. Zeiss SUPRA 55VP used for back-scatter images (BSEs) and microscope settings were as 20 kV acceleration voltage, aperture: 120, working distance 8.5 mm under mapping mode of 8% field overlap, 357.3x magnification, 2.5 μm step size (also pixel size) and 2000 counts in the spectrum, and 319 nm per pixel

size. In AQM-SEM, energy dispersive X-ray spectra were collected systematically covering a high-resolution grid in the analyzed Fe-bearing phases grains, and subsequently each individual EDS spectrum was identified as a phase.

An important role in such SEM-automated mineralogical studies was the definition of phases present in the investigated sample, as the AQM software requires this information to classify the phases based on the analyzed EDS spectra. The Mineralogic software allowed to optimize the mineral list and add unknown/ unclassified minerals/phases after the automated analysis. The manual SEM-EDS microanalyses prior to the automated analyses were performed to determine the elemental compositions of the particles and to divide them into distinct phases. The samples were analyzed at a magnification of 636x and a step size of 1.85 μm . Each phase was given a respective colour resulting in a false-colour mineral map of the analyzed sample area. In addition to the mineral maps, backscattered electron (BSE) micrographs of the analyzed areas were acquired automatically by the AQM software.

2.5. Thermomagnetic (TMA) measurements

The ground sample was subjected to a rotary splitter (Retsch, Germany) to obtain a representative sample for thermomagnetic (TMA) measurements. Temperature-dependent magnetic susceptibility tests were performed using (AGICO Inc., MFK1-FA Kappabridge, Brno, Czech Republic) equipped with a CS-4 furnace and a CS-L cryostat using an AF-field amplitude of 200 A m^{-1} (0.25 mT). A 0.1-0.2 g of specimen together with a test tube and thermometer were weighted. The equipment was run at elevated temperature, while the magnetic susceptibility was determined incrementally as the sample was heated from room temperature (25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) to 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and cooled down to 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Argon gas was injected into the tube with a flowrate of 6–8 L/h to inhibit the sample oxidation. The obtained results were analyzed through Cureval version 8.0.2 software. A detailed description of the measurement can be found elsewhere (McEnroe et al., 2022).

2.6. Magnetic and gravity separation experiments

To minimize grinding energy, first coarse feed sizes (i.e., -105+210, -500+210, and -1168+500 μm) were tested by different separation techniques, i.e. gravity (Mozley Table) and magnetic (wet high-intensity Slon[®], and Davis Tube, dry Rare Earth Roll Separator unit (6000-14000 G), dry roll separator (LRE 1005-1 model, Eriez magnetic Europ Ltd., United Kingdom, 3000-6000 G)). However, very little improvement was achieved with less than 10% mass recovery. For this reason, these results are not presented in this work. By further grinding to reach a desirable liberation degree, fraction size of <105 μm was chosen to be treated with one gravity method (Mozley SuperPanner, Richard Mozley Ltd, England) and two magnetic separators (i.e., Davis Tube and Slon[®] model 100 wet high-intensity separator (VPHGMS)). Figure 1 exhibits the particle size distribution of the feed to the three dedicated separators. As seen, the top size is 110 μm corresponding very well with the sieve analyses indicating d_{80} and d_{50} of ca. 85 and 42 μm , respectively.

Figure 1. Particle size distribution of feed sample subjected to separation processes

The Davis tube (0.02-0.6 T, Dings Magnetic Separator Co., U.S.A.) was operated in two magnetic fields, i.e., 2500 G and 3200 G, keeping the rest of operating parameters constant. It is worth noting that, a Gauss Meter (HIRST GM04, Norway) with two different probes (i.e., axial and transverse) was used for measuring the magnetic field for each equipment depending on the position of coils. For each test, 20 g of representative sample was under identical operation time. First, the strike was regulated to have 60 strokes/min, and the water flowrate was stabilized at 1 L/min. The prepared sample was added, and the non-magnetic sample was gathered from the bottom of the tube, while the magnetic product was obtained by disconnecting the magnetic field in the end of the experiment. The magnetic and non-magnetic products were filtered, dried over night at 60°C in a laboratory drier (Termaks series 9000, Norway), weighted, and then analyzed using the pXRF method. The mass recovery was calculated using the well-known equation as $R=P/F\times 100\%$, where $R(\%)$ is the mass recovery, $P(g)$ and $F(g)$ are the weights of separation product (either magnetic or non-magnetic) and feed, respectively.

Since the sample contains disseminated magnetite, the lowest level of magnetic intensity (1000 G) was applied using the Slon[®] separator. First, one cleaning stage was executed through flushing water through hoses and the equipment. Afterwards, a suitable matrix according to the particle range was opted. Later, the feed water flowrate given to the equipment was kept constant (5 L/min) using an adjustable pump. The water underflow was regulated in a way that the level of water in the cylinder was in the set point. The experiment was executed by applying 1000 G magnetic field as the minimum possible field, and the sample was added to the cylinder afterwards. The non-magnetic sample, first, was gathered until ensuring only water passes through the Slon[®]. After gathering the product, the magnetic field was reduced to zero and the magnetic product was collected. Both samples were filtered, dried, weighted and subjected to the pXRF analyses.

As described earlier, primary tests were performed on coarse fraction sizes, and the operating parameters were optimized as shortest position of strike, and 2.5 cm³/min water flowrate, the feed size of $d_{80}=85\ \mu\text{m}$ and experimental time=30 sec. This time level was opted based on the qualitative movement of slurry on the Mozley Table.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Sample characterization

Figure 2 demonstrates μCT images based on the absorbed X-rays by different entities within the sample. The red points represent magnetite, and it can be evidently seen that they are distributed throughout the sample. Since the magnetite has the specific gravity of 5.2 g/cm³, which is considerably higher than Al₂O₃, CaCO₃ and Na/Mg-bearing components, it is straightforward to refer these high attenuation entities to the magnetite as the target mineral which contains predominant proportion of the sample. However, it is important to mention that the sample includes Ti, Sc, Cr and rare earth elements (REE), which can also adsorb a high amount of X-rays that can make the distinguishing task a little difficult.

Figure 2. μCT images of H₂-reduced bauxite residue. Red spots represent the distribution of magnetite

Figure 3 exhibits the 3D perspective of the studied H₂-reduced bauxite residue sample under specific conditions given in Section 2.3. Figure 3a shows the 3D image constructed based on 2D images in different time frames, and Figure 3b represents the same sample distinguishing magnetite with the red spots. As seen, magnetite, the target mineral, is evenly distributed in the material's matrix, which is in line with the Fe content in different size fractions (Appendix A, Figure A1), and SEM-based automated mineralogy pictures represented in Section 3.3.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional μ CT reconstruction of H_2 -reduced bauxite residue sample: (a) general overview, and b) displayed magnetite grains

Table 1 presents the Fe content obtained using different characterization methods (i.e., ICP-MS, pXRF, SQ-XRD and, AM). As known, the most reliable approach is X-ray diffraction spectroscopy for this type of sample, which provided 22%. In addition to that the amount of Fe measured through the portable XRF device was 23%, which is almost in line with *ca.* 30% Fe given by the SQ-XRD analysis. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) resulted 25% Fe in the same sample. Despite the analytical techniques, given results are in good correlation with information presented by Pilla et al. (2022) which was 22.7%.

Table 1. Content of Fe measured by using different methods

Measurement method	ICP-MS	XRF	SQ-XRD	pXRF	AM
Fe content (wt%)	25	22	30	23	???

Figure 4 exhibits XRD patterns of the studied sample. As seen, the main Fe-bearing component is magnetite (Fe_3O_4) consisting of 43.3% of the sample. The most prevalent iron-containing phases were found as hematite (Fe_2O_3) and goethite ($FeOOH$) in the raw bauxite residue as major phases. Diaspore, gibbsite, bayerite, and boehmite are minerals that include aluminum phases. Both Perovskite and Anatase displayed titanium phases. In addition, the calcium mineral calcite and the sodium compound cancrinite were identified in the raw BR. After the reduction process under 5 vol% H_2 at 500 °C for 2 h with 20 wt% NaOH, the mineral phases of hematite and goethite were completely transformed into magnetite (which is having high magnetic susceptibility), and aluminum, cancrinite, and calcium phases were changed to water leachable sodium aluminate, sodium calcium silicate, sodium aluminum silicate. The phases of perovskite remain stable. As can be evidently identified from Figure 4, the picks are not

fully overlapped with the standard CCDs meaning some uncertainties in the results. This is related to the fact that the sample was already metallurgically treated at 500 °C and some phases were already changed during this process making it different than a typical primary ore type. However, the same nature of Fe was identified by the TMA, meaning with high confidence, that the main Fe-embedded composition was magnetite.

Figure 4. XRD patterns of the raw bauxite residue and the feed sample (H₂-reduced bauxite residue)

3.2. TMA analyses

Figure 5 represents the thermomagnetic behaviour of the sample versus high temperature change (50-750 °C). As can be seen, there is a sudden peak at 580 °C, which represents the Curie temperature/point of magnetite (Fabian et al., 2013). Red and blue curves represent measurements during heating and cooling, respectively. Additionally, the Hopkinson effect can be observed from the curve, which is a feature of ferromagnetic materials, in which an increase in the magnetic susceptibility is seen at temperatures between the blocking and Curie temperatures of the material. The Hopkinson effect can be observed as a peak in thermomagnetic curves that immediately precedes the susceptibility drop associated with the Curie temperature (Franco and Dodrill, 2021). In other words, Figure 5 demonstrates that the main iron-bearing component is magnetite, which is in line with the XRD results (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Thermomagnetic illustration of the feed sample (H_2 -reduced bauxite residue)

3.3. Automated mineralogy

Figure 6 exhibits the modal mineralogy of studied feed sample of H_2 -reduced bauxite residue (red mud). According to the results, magnetite, as the target mineral, contains only 2.4 wt% of the sample, and Fe is embedded in various forms. Other detected phases are different type of slags as follows: Slag_medium Fe+Ti (22.9 wt%), ii) Slag_Al-O_low Fe (1.3 wt%), iii) Slag_high Fe (2.1 wt%), iv) Slag_high Fe+Ti (5.6 wt%), v) Slag_low Fe+Ti (2.4 wt%), vi) Slag_medium Fe (3.5 wt%), vii) Slag_Na-O_Fe (34.3 wt%), viii) Slag_Na-O_high Fe (2.7 wt%), ix) Slag_Na-O_no Fe (21.4 wt%), and Others (1.3 wt%).

Distribution of Fe within different phases is shown in Figure B1 (Appendix B). It can be seen that the most Fe containing phase is the Slag_medium Fe+Ti with 35.14%, followed by Slag_Na-O_Fe constituting 23.34% Fe. However, another main phase (21.42 wt% of sample weight, Slag_Na-O_no Fe) does not contain any Fe. Therefore, approximately 58% of Fe is distributed between these two phases (respectively 22.96 wt% and 34.27 wt%).

Figure 7 represents BSE and mineralogical map pictures of the feed sample. Since the sample was 500-700 °C thermally treated, so-called phases are used instead of typical minerals, except magnetite which was 96% converted from hematite (Fe_2O_3) through H_2 -reduction process (Pillaet al., 2022). Similar to the μ -CT images (Figures 2-3), it is clear that Fe is evenly distributed in different grain sizes throughout the feed sample.

Figure 6. Modal mineralogy of the feed sample (H₂-reduced bauxite residue)

Figure 7. A demographic picture of a) BSE and b) mineral map pictures

Another important factor is the liberation degree of the target mineral in the sample. Table 2 presents the liberation degree of given phases in different locking classes. It is obvious that only 7% of magnetite has the liberation degree of >50% meaning that most of magnetite was intergrown with other phases. This value corresponds to 34% and 40% for two other main phases i.e., Slack_medium Fe+Ti and Slag_Na-O_Fe, respectively. In other words, most of particles and grains were locked with other phases hardening their potential separation efficiency.

Table 2. Classification of locking properties of the main detected phases

Phase	< 10	< 20%	< 30%	< 40%	< 50%	< 60%	< 70%	< 80%	< 90%	< 100%	= 100%
Magnetite	48.0	17.4	14.7	7.0	5.6	2.8	1.8	1.7	0.7	0.1	0.2
Slack_medium Fe+Ti	10.7	16.1	12.5	12.6	13.7	15.7	12.3	4.6	1.4	0.2	0.4
Slag_high Fe+Ti	48.9	31.1	12.4	4.3	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1
Slag_medium Fe	61.3	20.9	9.6	3.9	1.6	1.5	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1

Slag_Na-O_Fe	1.2	3.8	10.1	19.0	25.9	15.8	10.3	7.1	4.5	1.9	0.4
Slag_Na-O_no Fe	2.3	6.9	15.9	33.3	25.4	9.9	4.0	1.4	0.5	0.1	0.3

3.4. Magnetic and gravity separation results

Figure 8 shows the mass recovery and concentrated grade of Fe after gravity (Mozley Table) and magnetic (Slon[®], and Davis Tube) separation. As seen, applying Mozley Table enhanced the Fe content from 21-23% to 31% in the concentrate with the mass recovery of 52%. Slon[®] at 1000 G resulted in almost similar the Fe content (i.e., 33%) but with the maximum possible mass recovery of 80%. Using a single Davis Tube at a lower magnetic intensity of 2500 G showed around 18% improvement in Fe grade (from 22 to 40%), while the mass recovery was the most minimum among all equipment (22%). An enhancement in the magnetic field from 2500 to 3000 G induced an increase in the iron recovery from 21% to 32% but slightly diminished the iron grade from 40% to 36%. This is related to the fact that higher magnetic intensity was applied to the system having more potential force to recover mass. As known, the best separation process is the one which maximizes the grade and recovery simultaneously. However, according to the presented results in Figure 7, the maximum recovery of 80% was resulted from Slon[®], while the Davis Tube led maximized the Fe grade (40%). Such results show that one stage separation is not sufficient and whether continuous operations or back-to-back processes (scavenging and cleaning) should be included to reach a desirable selective separation. It should be noted that, further experiments should be conducted to validate the results from reproducibility point of view.

Figure 8. Grade and mass recovery of iron after gravity (Mozley Table) and magnetic separation (Slon, and Davis Tube)

Figure 9 shows an overview of mineralogical mapping of separation products. It is evident that magnetic products contain more magnetite (shown in red colour) even if in case of using gravity separator (Mozley Table) than the non-magnetic one. However, the slag (shown in dark and light green) is transported to the non-magnetic part due to the low liberation (Table 2) and association of Fe-bearing components with the non-magnetic ones. Other than this, the Davis Tube in both magnetic intensities shows excessive transportation of magnetic particles than the rest of devices which is well-correlated with the quantitative results shown in Figure 8.

Figure 10 illustrates that magnetite is the predominant mineral phase in magnetic concentrate, whereas perovskite and ilmenite were reported to have low peak intensities. This product can be further used as source for iron industries as an ingredient/ additive. In contrast, quartz, calcite, and perovskite phases were largely concentrated in non-magnetic tailings, but magnetite phases were still found, with lesser intensities. The non-magnetic fraction further can be utilized for extraction of REEs or making cement. In addition, the phases of water-leachable sodium aluminates dissipated in both magnetic and nonmagnetic fractions, indicating that these phases were dissolved in the liquor/water Byproduct.

Figure 9. Mineralogical overview of products from magnetic (Product 1 – magnetic, Product 2 – non-magnetic) and gravity (Product 1 – heavy, Product 2 – light) separation

Figure 10. XRD patterns of non-magnetic product (red lines), and magnetic (black lines) fraction of Davis Tube test (2500 G)

4. Conclusions

The current research work aimed at characterizing H₂-reduced bauxite residue (red mud), which was thermally treated at 500 °C and 5 vol% hydrogen for 2 h with 20 wt% NaOH. Qualitative μ -CT observations showed that the Fe-bearing component was evenly disseminated within the matrix of the studied sample. The TMA results indicated that the main Fe-embedded module was magnetite corresponding a sharp peak at the Curie temperature of 580 °C. The automated mineralogy data confirmed that magnetite as the target mineral contained only 2.35 wt% of the sample and Fe was mainly detected in slag phases including association with Ti (22.96 wt%), and Na (34.27 wt%). Although, one of the main phases as Slag_Na-O_no Fe included 21.42 wt% of the sample but it did not contain any iron component. Only 7% free liberation of magnetite was found at >50 μ m showing its intergrowth with other phases, while this value corresponded 34% and 40% for two other main phases i.e., Slack_medium Fe+Ti and Slag_Na-O_Fe, respectively. The experimental separation test results showed that using Slon[®] in batch condition led to the maximum mass recovery of 80% while operating Davis Tube maximized iron concentration to about 40%. Further scavenging and cleaning stages would be necessary to increase the grade and recovery to a specific extent.

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Appendix A

Distribution of Fe in different fraction sizes of H₂-reduced sample. As seen, the amount of Fe was almost identical in both fine and coarse fraction sizes.

Figure A1. Fe content in different fraction sizes

Appendix B

Complementary information given by the automated mineralogy. Figure B1 illustrates iron distribution in different phases identified through mineralogical mapping.

Figure B1. Fe distribution within identified main phases

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